

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15699314](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15699314)

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Assessing the radiation susceptibility of metal halide perovskite solar cells</i>
Project TA identifier	TA09-306
General application	<i>Space, Perovskite Solar Cells</i>
Type of test	<i>TNID, Proton bombardment</i>
Group leader, Institute	<i>Prof. Michael Saliba, Institute for Photovoltaics</i>
Co-authors, Institutes	<i>Claudiu Mortan, Institute for Photovoltaics</i>
Date(s) of the experiment	17.11.2023
Facility	<i>CNA (Centro Nacional de Aceleradores), Sevilla, Spain</i>
Amount of access granted	10 h

Objectives of the experiments

Metal halide perovskite based solar cells have achieved a power conversion efficiency of 27 % for single junction and 33 % for tandem cells. Due to the low cost, low mass, and the possibility to adopt flexibility, this class of solar cells is ideal to harvest solar energy in space applications. In terrestrial applications, perovskite solar cells are prone to damage from heat and humid weather. For space applications, humidity and molecular oxygen cannot impair device performance. However, cosmic rays and high-energy particle radiation will affect the solar cells' performance. With the proposed experiments, we investigated the influence of radiation dose on perovskite solar cell performance using proton radiation. We analyzed the radiation effects on different layers of the perovskite solar cells, as well as on the overall photo-conversion efficiency.

Experiment test report

The irradiation beam line of the 3MV Tandem Pelletron installed in the Centro Nacional de Aceleradores has been used to perform the irradiation tests. Seven groups of solar cells were supplied to be irradiated with protons, in static mode with the specified fluence. The boards were placed directly in the sample holder, designed, and manufactured to be used in the irradiation vacuum chamber. The samples were fitted by the CNA staff on the sample holder to obtain a homogeneous spot of 1 cm² size. Afterwards, it is scanning with a magnetic system increasing the full irradiation area. The total fluence is calculated based on the value of the particle density integrated in the complete area. Each group of samples has been simultaneously irradiated in one run to achieve the established total fluence, always at normal incidence geometry. The energy data (see Table) are obtained in base to the last calibration of the tandem accelerator (December 2023, internal document). The uncertainty associated with flux and fluence measurements is within 10%. The irradiation was performed at room temperature and the pressure in the chamber was 1x10⁻⁶ mbar. The details and data are presented in the table below. For simplicity, only a medium flux value will be presented, which is calculated based on pulses registered

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by the counter.

RUN	Energy (MeV)	Dv (cm)	DH (cm)	AREA (cm ²)	Time (s)	Fluence (p+/cm ²)	Medium Flux (p+/s·cm ²)
RUN D1.1	0.58 ± 0.04	17	17	289	8229	6.0E+13	7.3E+09
RUN D1.2	0.58 ± 0.04	17	17	289	7384	6.0E+13	8.1E+09
RUN D1.3	0.58 ± 0.02	17	17	289	7306	6.0E+13	8.2E+09
RUN D2.5	2.00 ± 0.06	12	14	168	3877	6.0E+13	1.6E+10
RUN D2.4	3.01 ± 0.12	12	14	168	4124	6.0E+13	1.5E+10
RUN D3.6	0.99 ± 0.01	12	14	168	3912	6.0E+13	1.5E+10
RUN D3.7	0.99 ± 0.01 (*)	12	14	168	4032	6.0E+13	1.5E+10

(*) During this run, a 20 um Aluminium foil was used to obtain an energy below 600 keV, the minimum energy provided by the Tandem machine. In a first calculation with SRIM (Stopping Range Tables), the estimated energy was 50 keV on the samples using the 20 um Aluminium.

The perovskite samples have been brought back to the Institute for Photovoltaics and numerous material characterization methods have been employed, including Photoluminescence (PL), Time resolved photoluminescence (TRPL), UV/Vis spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to assess the materials change after the proton bombardment. We are currently preparing several publications in peer-reviewed journals about our findings.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101008126.